

Water Activity and its Modification through Humectants in Foods

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INTRODUCTION

Water is the most important diluent of water-soluble food components and plasticizer (softener) of various water miscible polymeric compounds as well as often the main food component. Chemical reactions, enzymatic changes, and microbial growth may occur readily in foods with high water contents when their occurrence is not restricted by environmental factors such as pH or temperature. Water has several effects on food stability, palatability and overall quality. The physicochemical state of water is related to water activity (a_w) which is a measure of water availability for the growth of various microorganisms and physicochemical stability of high-moisture foods. Water as a plasticizer has an additional effect on the shelf life of low-moisture and intermediate-moisture foods.

Rates of deteriorative changes and microbial growth at normal food storage conditions often depend on water content and a_w . Food deterioration due to microbial growth is not likely to occur at $a_w < 0.6$. However, chemical reactions and enzymatic changes may occur at considerably lower water activities. Typical deteriorative changes of low-moisture foods include enzyme-catalyzed changes, non-enzymatic browning and oxidation. Enzymatic changes and non-enzymatic browning have been found to occur above critical water content and show a rate maximum at an intermediate-moisture level which is followed by a decrease at higher water activities. Oxidation may have a high rate at low water contents, the rate may go through a minimum with a decrease in a_w and then it may decrease at higher water activities.

WATER ACTIVITY AND FOOD PRESERVATION

The control of the moisture content in the processing of foods is an ancient method of preservation. Description of preservation by sun drying can be found in the Bible, in ancient Egyptian Hieroglyphics and in the Journals of Marco Polo (Labuza, 1976). Later, meats also were preserved through the addition of salt (Scott, 1993). The principle of these processes is the control of the water content by either removing water or binding it in such away that the food becomes stable to both microbial and chemical deterioration (Labuza, 1980). The physical-chemical basis by which this occurs was not really understood until the late 1950s when Scott (1957) and Salwin (1959) independently introduced the concept of water activity.

Since the microbial degradation of food products is related to water activity, this is an important characteristic of foods (Erickson, 1982). Rao (1993) has shown that water activity is a parameter in preservation of foodstuffs. Rockland and Nishi (1980) have also shown that water activity influences the food quality and stability.

It has been realized that not all water present in a food is available for microbial growth. Some of the water present in a food exists tightly bound to the product and hence can not be utilized by microbes. The bound water increases when; some solutes (humectants) are added to a product (Sperber, 1983).

Thus, it is clear that the state of water rather than total content of water is important as far as microbial proliferation is concerned. It has been observed that the state of water is related to the vapour pressure of a food. Greater the proportion of free water present, greater is the vapour pressure and vice versa. Increased bound water reduces vapour pressure (Scott, 1957). Thus if a product is kept in a closed container and allowed to equilibrate, the relative humidity inside the

container will be a measure of free state of water inside the product. The distilled water shows a relative humidity of 100% and all foods show a relative humidity of less than 100%. A definite correlation between the relative humidity of a food and microbial growth was observed by Scott (1957). For convenience, he expressed the relative humidity of a food in decimals and called it water activity of the food.

Concerning usage and definitions, water activity was used to indicate an intrinsic parameter of a food system and equilibrium relative humidity a property of the surrounding atmosphere in equilibrium with the food system under consideration (Berg and Bruin, 1981). Kaplow (1970) also mentioned the method for determining the amount of water available for microbial growth in a substance by measuring the vapour pressure of water above the substance. This vapour pressure is most meaningfully expressed by dividing it by the vapour pressure of pure water at the same temperature and the same total pressure. The fraction called, water activity, is a measure of the effective concentration of water in the substance.

$$\%ERH = \frac{V^1P}{VP} \times 100$$

$$a_w = \frac{V^1P}{VP}$$

$$\text{Thus } \Rightarrow \frac{\%ERH}{100}$$

Where, a_w is water activity, V^1P is vapour pressure of a food, VP is vapour pressure of pure water and % ERH is the equilibrium relative humidity, at which food neither gains nor loses water.

At high moisture contents foods have water activity close to 1.0. This activity is comparable to that of dilute solutions. At these high water activities, food deterioration can be caused by progress of enzymatic, chemical and microbial processes (Labuza *et al.*, 1974).

The concept of water activity is now widely used by the food industry. Intermediate-moisture foods and other water activity or moisture-adjusted foods receive an increasing interest from the industry. Therefore, only within recent decades it has been recognized that the chemical, physical, textural properties and hence the quality and stability of food products are related directly to the equilibrium relative humidity (ERH) or their water activity, (Scott, 1957; Bone, 1973; Troller, 1980; Webster *et al.*, 1985 and Leistner, 1992).

Water Activity and Microbial Growth

The most important genera from the standpoint of food spoilage are *Pseudomonas*, *Achromobacter*, *Lactobacillus*, *Proteus*, *Micrococcus* and *Bacillus*. However, in canned foods spore bearing bacteria namely *Bacillus* and *clostridium* are of greatest concern. Most of the bacteria cease to grow below a_w 0.95, but *Bacilli* can multiply even at a_w 0.91 and *Staphylococci* below 0.90 a_w . The limiting a_w for microbial growth also changes depending on the type of solute. For example, *Clostridium perfringens* is inhibited at a_w 0.97 - 0.95, when NaCl, KCl or sucrose are used in the growth medium, but when glycerol is used to adjust the a_w , the limiting a_w for growth

TABLE 1 Water Activity Limits for the Growth of Different Microorganisms

Organism	Water Activity below which Growth is Inhibited
Gram-ve rods, bacterial spores and some yeasts	0.95
Most cocci, <i>Lactobacilli</i> , <i>Bacilli</i> and some molds	0.91
Most yeasts	0.87
Most molds, <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.80 - 0.75
Xerophilic molds	0.65
Osmophilic yeasts	0.60

Source: Davies et al, 1976

of the same may be lowered to 0.93. The growth limits of different bacteria are shown in Table 1.

It is not yet completely clear as to why some bacteria are liable to tolerate and grow at low a_w . The selective permeability of bacterial membranes may play an important role in resisting the low a_w . Ionic strength of cytoplasm in all microorganisms is maintained at a level which is optimum for their metabolic activity. This limits the osmotic pressure which determines the flow of water in and out of the cell. When bacterial cells are exposed to high ionic strength environment (low a_w) the water flows out of the cells to maintain equilibrium increasing the ionic strength inside the cells. Thus the metabolic activity is reduced and at some level it is stopped. However, some types of bacteria (*Staphylococcus*, *Bacillus*) and molds adapt themselves to adverse conditions (Sperber, 1983). Bacterial resistance to external heat also depends on a_w of media. Decreased a_w increases bacterial resistance to heat. For example, at a_w 1.00 it takes heating at 100°C for just less than a second to kill 90% of *Clostridium botulinum* type E organism, whereas it takes 2 h to kill the same number of bacteria at a_w 0.2 (Frazier and Westhoff, 1984).

WATER ACTIVITY AND FOOD SPOILAGE

Water activity profoundly influences spoilage of foods. Spoilage of foods is mainly because of proteolysis, lipolysis and oxidation reactions. Proteolytic and lipolytic spoilage are brought by the action of enzymes-bacterial or native. The enzymatic action is controlled by altering the reactant mobility. Proteolysis and lipolysis are accelerated at high a_w because of increased reactant mobility. But chemical spoilage like non-enzymatic browning and oxidation are affected in different ways. The non-enzymatic browning rate generally increases with increasing a_w at low moisture range, reaches a maximum at a_w 0.4 to 0.8 and decreases with a further increase in a_w . Besides the mobility and dilution factors, water may affect non-enzymatic browning by inhibiting or enhancing some of the intermediate reactions. Extent of browning also depends on the type of humectant. Glycerol may cause increase in apparent browning. Sodium chloride has no effect, while use of monosaccharides will markedly increase browning.

Water has an interesting effect on oxidation of lipids. It acts both as antioxidant and pro-oxidant. At a_w below the monolayer value, oxidation rate decreases with increasing a_w . The rate reaches minimum at the monolayer value and increases with a further increase in a_w . Antioxidant effect of water at low a_w has been attributed to bonding of hydroperoxides and hydration of metal catalysts, whereas the pro-oxidant effect of water at higher a_w is due to increased mobility of the reactants (Hiedelbaugh and Karel, 1970). Water activity of some of the common foods is listed in Table. 2

MODIFICATION OF WATER ACTIVITY

The stability and safety of food does improve if water activity of the product decreases. Several soluble substances like salt, sugar etc. that are added to aqueous phase of the food to reduce water activity are called humectants (Kaplou, 1970; Bone, 1973). Karel (1976) and Hiedalbaugh and Karel (1975)

TABLE 2 Water Activity of Some Foods

Name of Food	Water Activity
Mayonnaise	0.910
Margarine	0.950
Textured Soy Protein	0.530
Plum Marmalade	0.910
Processed Cheese Spread	0.965
Dried Yeast	0.176
Yeast Extract	0.592
Dried Whole Milk	0.509
Dried Skim Milk	0.259
Processed Cheese	0.965
Kashkaval Cheese (10 month old)	0.930-0.965
Unsalted Butter	0.990
Salted Butter	0.920
Khoa	0.960
Milk Chocolate	0.600
Apples	0.980
Apricot	0.985
Bananas	0.964-0.987
Cherries	0.960-986
Currants	0.990
Dates	0.974
Figs	0.974
Grapes	0.963-0.986
Lemon	0.982-0.984
Mangoes	0.979-0.987
Papaya	0.990
Pineapple	0.985-0.988
Plums	0.969-0.982
Strawberry	0.986-0.991
Water melon	0.992
Beans	0.990-0.996
Beets	0.979-0.985
Cabbage	0.990-0.992
Carrots	0.983-0.989
Tomatoes	0.991-0.994
Camembert Cheese	0.967
Sandesh Narampak	0.920

have divided the process of a_w modification into (a) moist infusion in which normal-moisture solid food pieces are soaked, and/or cooked in an appropriate solution to obtain a product with desired a_w , (b) dry infusion in which solid food pieces are first dehydrated following which they are infused by soaking in a solution containing the desired osmotic agents, and (c) blending in which the components are weighed, blended, cooked and extruded or otherwise combined to obtain a product with desired water activity.

HUMECTANTS

Humectants are the compounds which bind free water and decrease the a_w of a solution or a product. The water activity reducing ability of humectants depends on their molecular weight/equivalent weight. By Raoult's law, water activity of a food can be approximated as —

$$a_w = \frac{N_1}{N_1 + N_2}$$

Where a_w = water activity
 N_1 = moles of water in the product
 N_2 = moles of humectant in the product

TABLE 3. Water Activity Lowering Ability of Common Humectants used in Foods

Humectant	Molecular Weight	a_w of 10% Solution
Sucrose	342.3	0.992
Glucose	181.15	0.991
Fructose	190.16	0.990
Glycerol	95.12	0.981
Sodium chloride	58.44	0.931

Source: Lerici et al. 1983

Other equations reported in literature (Norrish, 1966; Ross, 1975; Chaung and Toledo, 1976; Solan and Labuza, 1976) can also be used. These are a slight improvement over Raoult's law, but still Raoult's law is the simplest to work with. In place of equations, water activity tables of Robinson and Stokes (1968) can also be used. Generally, when more than one humectants are used, they will have additive effect on a_w reduction. Water activity lowering ability of some humectants commonly used in foods is shown in Table 3. Salt is a common food additive and it is usual to add this to the limit of normal seasoning. Among other components, glycerol approaches the requirements of an ideal solute for foods. Other humectants are protein hydrolysates, starch hydrolysates, sugars etc.

In choosing a solute or humectant for water activity control, some of the factors to consider are flavour, solubility, molecular weight, ionization, nutrition, compatibility with food factors; pH, physiological limits and shelf life (Bone, 1973).

Ideally, the humectants when added to a food should not modify its normal organoleptic qualities. Such compounds should be stable, nonvolatile, highly soluble in water, chemically inert, edible in large quantities and if possible, metabolized *in vivo* as a source of energy (Ledward, 1985).

The solute can be sugars, polyhydric alcohols, neutral salts, certain acids and bases (Bone, 1973; Solan and Labuza, 1976). Food additives like strong electrolytes have also been studied by Benmergani et al., (1979) to be used as a depressant.

All humectants so far studied fall short of the ideal requirements. Bitter after taste of propylene glycol, the kerosene note of glycerin, the sweetness of sugars and the destruction of protein quality by reducing sugars restrict the use of humectants in increased limits (Bone, 1973). However, salt and sugar have been successfully used as humectants in many traditional intermediate-moisture foods (Eirckson, 1982).

Use of common humectants (salt and sugar) has also been advocated to avoid chemical overloading of these foods. (Leistner, 1992). The physiological implication of high salt intake and sweet taste imparted by sucrose limit their use in large quantities (Patil and Singh, 1998). Feeding high levels of dietary glycerol to rats have been shown to result in an accumulation of lipids in blood serum and the liver. Attempts have been made to find other suitable humectants for use in foods. Glycine and protein hydrolysate seem promising but their high cost and adverse effect of protein hydrolysate on flavour may restrict their use in lower concentrations only (Chrife et al., 1980; Vallejo-Cardobe et al., 1986).

Brimelow (1985) emphasized the need to investigate the water activity reducing properties of naturally occurring edible substances such as plant and fruit extract. Patil and Singh (1998) have shown that pumpkin syrup solids can be a very promising humectant for use in intermediate-moisture foods, intended for human consumption as it has water binding capacity close to glycerol and has pleasant flavour and relatively low sweetness intensity. It can thus be added in large quantities (up to a maximum of 16%) without

substantially influencing the flavour of the food. Similarly, a branched oligosaccharides (BOS) mixture prepared from liquefied corn starch using *Bacillus licheniformis* and concentrated by removing glucose and maltose through yeast fermentation, has also been used as a humectant in bread making (Yoo et al., 1995). The use of BOS concentrate in place of sucrose has indicated to be advantageous, as it may stimulate microbial growth and/or Maillard browning. Polyols have been ascribed the most desirable humectants from a water holding stand point.

Humectants may also have protective effect on bacteria, as observed with *S. thermophilus* and *L. bulgaricus* during the storage of yoghurt. Among bacteria, some of the halophilics can grow at low a_w . *S. aureus* grows at a_w of as low as 0.80 (Davies et al., 1976). Minimum a_w for bacterial growth depends on the type of solute employed. *S. cremoris* had minimum a_w of 0.95 for its growth, when glycerol was used and it was 0.97, when sucrose was used. The corresponding values for *S. diacetylactis* and *S. lactis* were 0.95 and 0.95, 0.93 and 0.97, respectively. Minimal a_w for acid production, spore germination and growth is affected by the types of humectants used for adjusting a_w . Humectants can be mineral salts (NaCl in cheese), organic acids (lactic acid), mono- and oligo saccharides (sucrose and lactose), alcohols and polyols (glycerol and sorbitol in pastry), proteins and protein derivatives (amino acids in cheese) and lipids and lipid derivatives (fatty acids, phospholipids, emulsifiers and emulsions). Glucose has an additional inhibitory effect that is caused by decreasing a_w . Among glucose, NaCl, glycerol, glycine, proline, alanine, sodium glutamate and lysine hydrochloride as humectants, glycine was found to be the most effective and glycerol was the least effective in retarding the growth of lactic acid bacteria.

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